

New records of lithobiid centipedes (Chilopoda: Lithobiomorpha) from Middle Asia

Yurii V. Dyachkov¹

1 Altai State University, Barnaul, 61 Lenina Ave., 656049, Russia

Corresponding author: Yurii V. Dyachkov (dyachkov793@mail.ru)

Academic editor: R. Yakovlev | Received 29 July 2022 | Accepted 17 August 2022 | Published 19 September 2022

<http://zoobank.org/F1F161E2-BDDB-449A-AAE2-8B3D23CDAF7C>

Citation: Dyachkov YuV (2022) New records of lithobiid centipedes (Chilopoda: Lithobiomorpha) from Middle Asia. Acta Biologica Sibirica 8: 399–407. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7703408>

Abstract

The following taxa are new to the fauna of Uzbekistan: *Australobius* Chamberlin, 1920, *A. magnus* (Trotzina, 1894), *Hessebius* Verhoeff, 1941, *H. plumatus* Zalesskaja, 1978, *Lithobius praeditus* Zalesskaja, 1975, and *L. javanicus* (Zalesskaja, 1978). Order Lithobiomorpha is new to the Qashqadaryo and Surxondaryo regions of Uzbekistan; *A. magnus* is new to the Talas, Jalal-Abad, Chuy, and Batken regions of Kyrgyzstan. All the records are mapped.

Keywords

Australobius, biodiversity, fauna, *Hessebius*, Kyrgyzstan, Lithobiidae, new records, Uzbekistan

Introduction

A recent checklist (Dyachkov et al. 2022) contains 49 species arranged in 10 genera and 3 families from Middle Asia; it is also shown that not all the regions are studied evenly. This paper provides new faunistic records of lithobiid centipedes from poorly studied regions of Uzbekistan and Kyrgyzstan.

Material and methods

Specimens were taken by hand and preserved in 70% ethanol. The materials are deposited in ASU and ZISP (see abbreviations below).

Localities are indicated similar to those in the original labels; additional information is provided in square brackets. “Shiblyak” is a shrubland biome, typically consisting of densely growing xerophilous shrubs. Localities were mapped (Figs 1–4) with SimpleMapp (Shorthouse 2010).

Abbreviations: ad. – adult, AF – A.A. Fomichev, Afg – Afghanistan, AK – A.N. Kirichenko, ASU – Altai State University (Barnaul), B – Barschevsky, coll. – collector, fragm. – fragment, juv. – juvenile, K – Korzhynsky, Kg – Kyrgyzstan, LB – L. Berg, M – Molchanov, sad. – subadult, Tj – Tajikistan, Tu – Turkmenistan, Uz – Uzbekistan, YD – Yu.V. Dyachkov, ZISP – Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences (Saint Petersburg).

Results

Genus *Australobius* Chamberlin, 1920

Australobius magnus (Trotzina, 1894)

Figure 1

Material. 1 sad. ♀, 1 juv. ♀ (ASU No. 435), Uzbekistan, Surxondaryo Region, 28 km SE from Denau City, Babatag Mt. Range, N38°06'57", E68°11'54", *Pistacia* woodland and dry river bottom, in soil, under stones, 900–1200 m, 29–30 April 2022, coll. YD; 1♂, 3♀♀, 1 juv. ♀ (ASU No. 475), 35 km NW from Denau City, Baysun-Tau Mt. Range, Sangardakdarya River Valley, N38°31'31", E67°36'27", stony shiblyak with rocks, 1200 m, 4 May 2022, coll. AF; 4♂♂, 5♀♀, 4 juv. ♂, 7 juv. ♀ (ASU No. 439), 6♂♂, 5♀♀, 3 juv. (ASU No. 451), 2♂♂, 4♀♀, 1 juv. ♀ (ASU No. 466), 5 km N from Derbent City, Baysun-Tau Mt. Range, N38°15'03", E67°01'13", stony shiblyak with rocks, under stones, 1100–1400 m, 5 May 2022, coll. YD, AF; 11♂♂ (ASU No. 447), 14♂♂, 4 juv. (ASU No. 460), Kugitangtau Mt. Range, vicinity of Neftchi summer camp, stony *Juniperus* woodland, under stones, N37°51'32", E66°38'04", 1700–2000 m, 7–9 May 2022, coll. YD; 3♂♂ (ASU No. 472), 2♀♀ (ASU No. 463), vicinity of Neftchi summer camp, stony *Juniperus* woodland, under stones, N37°51'41", E66°37'38", 1700–2000 m, 6–7 May 2022, coll. AF; 5♂♂, 2♀♀ (ASU No. 456), Tupalangdarya River Valley, 7 km NNE from Gisarak Kishlak, stony shiblyak with rocks, under stones, N38°37'58", E67°49'32", 1100–1300 m, 1–2 May 2022, coll. YD; 3 juv. ♀, 1 fragm. (ASU No. 452), Qashqadaryo Region, Kyzylarya River Valley, vicinity of Suvlisay Kishlak, N38°49'37", E67°06'21", stony shiblyak with rocks, under stones, 1200 m, 8–10 May 2022, coll. YD; 1♀ (ZISP chilo-31), Kishlak Shut [ca. N39°8'47", E67°33'56"], 5 June 1896, coll. B; 1♂ (ZISP chilo-22), [Kyrgyzstan], [Osh

Region, Chong-Alay District], Daraut-Kurgan [Daroot-Korgon, ca. N39°33'12", E72°12'0"], 29 March 1913, coll. M; 1 ♀ (ZISP chilo-26), [Jalal-Abad Region, Suzak District], Fergana, Kogart River Valley [ca. N41°8'6", E73°37'39"], 6100 ft. [ca. 1980 m], under stones, 5 August 1895, coll. K; 1 ♂ (ZISP chilo-28), 1 ♂ (ZIN chilo-32), [Batken Region], Andarak [ca. N39°45'0", E69°27'36"], 17 and 25 June 1906, coll. LB; 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀ (ZISP chilo-24), [Talas Region], NW slope of Aleksandrovsky [Kyrgyz Ala-Too] Mt. Range, Makbal Mt. Pass [ca. N42°44'45", E72°4'58"], 9870 ft. [ca. 3000 m], 2–3 June 1910, coll. AK; 1 juv. ♂ (ZISP chilo-10), Chuy Region, Ala-Archa [national park, ca. N42°38', E74°28'], 800 m, 28 April, year and coll. unknown.

Distribution. Southern Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan (Trotzina 1894; Attems 1904; Zaleskaja 1978; Eason 1997; Dyachkov et al. 2022), Uzbekistan (new), Western China (Karakorum) (Eason 1997; Ma et al. 2014), and Eastern Nepal (Eason 1989, 1997).

Remarks. This species and genus *Australobius* are new to the fauna of Uzbekistan and to the Jalal-Abad, Talas, Chuy, and Batken regions of Kyrgyzstan.

Figure 1. Distribution of *Australobius magnus* (Trotzina, 1894) in Middle Asia: yellow circle – new data, violet one – literature data.

Genus *Hessebius* Verhoeff, 1941

Hessebius plumatus Zaleskaja, 1978

Figure 2

Material. 2 ♀♀ (ASU No. 431), Uzbekistan, Surxondaryo Region, 28 km SE from Denau City, Babatag Mt. Range, N38°06'57", E68°11'54", *Pistacia* woodland and dry river bottom, in soil, under stones, 900–1200 m, 29–30 April 2022, coll. YD; 3 ♀♀ (ASU No. 438), Baysun-Tau Mt. Range, 5 km N from Derbent City, N38°15'03",

E67°01'13", stony shiblyak with rocks, under stones, 1100–1400 m, 5 May 2022, coll. YD; 2♀♀ (ASU No. 446), Kugitangtau Mt. Range, vicinity of Neftchi summer camp, N37°51'32", E66°38'04", stony *Juniperus* woodland, under stones, 1700–2000 m, 7–9 May 2022, coll. YD; 2♂♂ (ASU No. 470), N37°51'41", E66°37'38", 6–7 May 2022, coll. AF; 1♂ (ZISP chilo-7), [Qashqadaryo Region], Kishlak Shut [ca. N39°8'47", E67°33'56"], 5 June 1896, coll. B.

Distribution. Middle Asia: Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan (Zalesskaja 1978; Bragina et al. 2020; Dyachkov 2019a, 2020; Dyachkov et al. 2022), and Uzbekistan (new).

Remarks. This species and genus *Hessebius* are new to the fauna of Uzbekistan.

Figure 2. Distribution of *Hessebius plumatus* Zalesskaja, 1978 in Middle Asia: yellow circle – new data, violet one – literature data, green circle – uncertain locality (see Dyachkov et al. 2022: 168).

Genus *Lithobius* Leach, 1814***Lithobius (Ezembius) praeditus* Zalesskaja, 1975**

Figure 3

Material. 5♂♂, 4♀♀ (ASU No. 478), Uzbekistan, Surxondaryo Region, 35 km NW from Denau City, Baysun-Tau Mt. Range, Sangardakdarya River Valley, N38°31'31", E67°36'27", stony shiblyak with rocks, under stones, 1200 m, 4 May 2022, coll. YD; 6♂♂, 14♀♀, 3 juv. ♀ (ASU No. 482), Tupalangdarya River Valley, 7 km NNE from Gisarak Kishlak, N38°37'58", E67°49'32", stony shiblyak with rocks, under stones, 1100–1300 m, 1–2 May 2022, coll. YD.

Distribution. Tajikistan (Zalesskaja 1975, 1978; Dyachkov et al. 2022) and Uzbekistan (new).

Remarks. This species is new to the fauna of Uzbekistan.

Figure 3. Distribution of *Lithobius praeditus* Zalesskaja, 1975 in Middle Asia: yellow circle – new data, violet one – literature data, green circle – uncertain locality (see Dyachkov et al. 2022: 169).

***Lithobius (Monotarsobius) javanicus* (Zalesskaja, 1978)**

Figure 4

Material. 2♀♀ (ASU No. 462), Uzbekistan, Surxondaryo Region, 28 km SE from Denau City, Babatag Mt. Range, N38°06'57", E68°11'54", *Pistacia* woodland and dry river bottom, in soil, under stones, 900–1200 m, 29–30 April 2022, coll. YD.

Distribution. Tajikistan (Zalesskaja 1978; Dyachkov et al. 2022) and Uzbekistan (new).

Remarks. This species is new to the fauna of Uzbekistan.

Figure 4. Distribution of *Lithobius javanicus* (Zalesskaja, 1978) in Middle Asia: yellow circle – new data, violet one – literature data.

Conclusions

Thus, at least 26 species arranged in 15 genera, 8 families, and 4 orders of Chilopoda are known from Uzbekistan (Kessler 1874; Sseliwanoff 1879, 1881a, 1881b, 1884; Pocock 1891; Attems 1904; Lignau 1929a, 1929b; Verhoeff 1930; Titova 1969, 1975, 1978; Zalesskaja 1972, 1975, 1978; Dobroruka 1979; Würmli 1975; Zalesskaja and Schileyko 1991, 1992; Dyachkov 2019b; Dyachkov and Nedoev 2021; Dyachkov and Bonato 2022; Dyachkov et al. 2022).

It should be recognized that our knowledge of Middle Asian lithobiomorph species is still far from being complete.

Acknowledgments

I wish to thank Muhammadto'ychi Rahimov (Samarkand, Uzbekistan) and Roman V. Yakovlev (ASU) for organizing the expedition. I am grateful to Alexander A. Fomichev (ASU) who donated the material and to Mariia A. Iuzhakova (Tomsk, Russia) who checked the English of an advanced draft. I wish to thank anonymous reviewers for corrections and critical commenting of the manuscript. This study was supported in the framework of "Priority-2030" Program by the Altai State University.

References

- Attems CG (1904) Central-und hoch-asiatische Myriopoden. Gesammelt im Jahre 1900 von Dr. von Almassy und Dr. von Stummer. Zoologische Jahrbücher 20: 113–130.
- Bragina TM, Dyachkov YuV, Farzalieva GSh (2020) New data on the centipede fauna (Myriapoda: Chilopoda) of Kostanay region, Kazakhstan. Far Eastern Entomologist 406: 27–32. <https://doi.org/10.25221/fee.406.4>
- Dobroruka LJ (1979) Zur weiteren kenntnis der zentralasiatischen chilopoden. Věstník Československé Společnosti Zoologicke 43 (3): 161–164.
- Dyachkov YuV (2019a) New data on lithobiomorph centipedes (Chilopoda: Lithobiomorpha: Anopsobiidae, Henicopidae, Lithobiidae) from Kazakhstan. Arthropoda Selecta 28 (1): 8–20. <https://doi.org/10.15298/arthsel.28.1.02>
- Dyachkov YuV (2019b) New data on the family Mecistocephalidae Bollman, 1893 (Chilopoda: Geophilomorpha) from Middle Asia. Arthropoda Selecta 28 (3): 368–373. <https://doi.org/10.15298/arthsel.28.3.02>
- Dyachkov YuV (2020) New data on the centipede (Chilopoda) fauna from Tajikistan. Ecologica Montenegrina 36: 78–86. <http://dx.doi.org/10.37828/em.2020.36.6>
- Dyachkov YuV, Nedoev KhKh (2021) A contribution to the centipede (Chilopoda: Geophilomorpha, Scolopendromorpha) fauna of Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan. Ecologica Montenegrina 41: 41–50. <http://dx.doi.org/10.37828/em.2021.41.6>
- Dyachkov YuV, Farzalieva GSh, Tuf IH (2022) An annotated checklist of centipedes (Chilopoda) of Middle Asian countries, part 1. Lithobiomorpha. Zootaxa 5100 (2): 151–188. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5100.2.1>
- Dyachkov YuV, Bonato L (2022) Morphology and distribution of the Middle Asian centipede genus *Krateraspis* Lignau, 1929 (Chilopoda, Geophilomorpha, Mecistocephalidae). ZooKeys 1095: 143–164. <https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.1095.80806>
- Eason EH (1989) Lithobiidae from the Nepal Himalayas with descriptions of ten new species of *Lithobius* and *Australobius* (Chilopoda: Lithobiomorpha). Zoologische Jahrbücher Abteilung für Systematik 116: 335–372.
- Eason EH (1997) On some Lithobiomorpha from the mountains of Kirghizia and Kazakhstan (Chilopoda). Arthropoda Selecta 6 (1/2): 117–121.

- Kessler K (1874) On Russian centipedes (Scolopendridae et Geophilidae). Trudy Russkago Entomologicheskago Obshchestva 8 (1): 28–45. [In Russian]
- Lignau NG (1929a) Zur Kenntnis der zentralasiatischen Myriopoden. Zoologischer Anzeiger 85 (5/8): 159–175.
- Lignau NG (1929b) Neue Myriopoden aus Zentralasien. Zoologischer Anzeiger 85 (9/10): 205–217.
- Ma H, Pei S, Hou X, Zhu T, Wu D, Gai Y (2014) An annotated checklist of Lithobiomorpha of China. Zootaxa 3847 (3): 333–358. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.3847.3.2>
- Pocock RI (1891) Descriptions of some new Geophilidae in the collection of the British Museum. Annals and Magazine of Natural History 6 (8): 215–227.
- Shorthouse DP (2010) SimpleMappr, an online tool to produce publication-quality point maps. <http://www.simplemappr.net>
- Sseliwanoff AV (1879) *Bothriogaster*, eine neue Gattung aus der Familie der Geophiliden. Zoologischer Anzeiger 2: 620–624.
- Sseliwanoff AV (1881a) Geophilidae from the Museum of Imperial Academy of Sciences. Zapiski Imperatorskoi Akademii Nauk 40: 1–27 [In Russian]
- Sseliwanoff AV (1881b) Turkestanskiya stonozhki (Geophilidae Leach). Izvestiya Imperatorskago Obshchestva Lyubitelei Estestvoznaniya, Antropologii i Etnografii pri Imperatorskom Moskvovskom Universitete 37: 229–232 [In Russian]
- Sseliwanoff AV (1884) Materials towards the study of Russian myriapods. Trudy Russkago Entomologicheskago obshchestva. St. Petersburg 18: 69–121. [In Russian]
- Titova LP (1969) Geophilids of the USSR fauna and news in the distribution of the fam. Mecistocephalidae. In: Aleinikova MM (Ed.). Problems of soil zoology, Materials of the 3rd All-Union Conference, Kazan, 1969. Nauka, Moscow, 165–166. [In Russian]
- Titova LP (1975) Geophilids of the family Mecistocephalidae (Chilopoda) in the fauna of the USSR. Zoologicheskii Zhurnal 54: 39–48. [In Russian with English summary]
- Titova LP (1978) Distribution of the geophilomorph family Himantariidae Cook. in the USSR. In: Sushchenya LM, Hotko EI (Eds.). Problems of soil zoology, Materials of the 6th All-Union Conference, Minsk. "Nauka i Tekhnika" Publishers, Minsk, 241. [In Russian]
- Trotzina A (1894) Vier neue *Lithobius*-Arten aus Central Asia. Horae Societatis Entomologicae Rossicae 28: 247–253.
- Verhoeff KW (1930) Über Myriapoden aus Turkestan. Zoologischer Anzeiger 91 (9/12): 243–266.
- Würmli M (1975) Revision der Hundertfüsser-Gattung *Thereuonema* (Chilopoda: Scutigeridae). Entomologica Germanica 2 (2): 189–196.
- Zalesskaja NT (1972) New species of genus *Esastigmatobius* (Lithobiomorpha, Henicopidae). Zoologicheskii zhurnal 51 (4): 608–611. [In Russian]
- Zalesskaja NT (1975) New lithobiomorph genera and species (Chilopoda, Lithobiomorpha) from Middle Asia and Far East. Zoologicheskii zhurnal 54 (9): 1316–1325. [In Russian]
- Zalesskaja NT (1978) Identification book of the lithobiomorph centipedes of the USSR (Chilopoda: Lithobiomorpha). Nauka publ., Moscow, 212 pp. [In Russian]

- Zalesskaja NT, Schileyko AA (1991) The scolopendromorph centipedes (Chilopoda, Scolopendromorpha). Nauka, Moscow, 102 pp. [In Russian]
- Zalesskaja NT, Schileyko AA (1992) The distribution of Scolopendromorpha in the USSR (Chilopoda). *Berichte des naturwissenschaftlichen-medizinischen Vereins Innsbruck* 10: 367–372.